

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Colour	%Cd		%Sulphur		ΔM mhos cm^{-2}	$\nu(C-S)$	$\nu(C=S)$	$\nu(C-N)$	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu(M-S)$
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.						
P-dtc	White	—	—	—	—	—	890	1260	1430	—	—
M-dtc	do	—	—	—	—	—	895	1250	1425	—	—
Cd(P-dtc) ₂	White amorphous	25.67	25.99	29.42	29.60	6.5	875	1220	1435	350	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ Py	Brown, crystalline	21.42	21.76	24.29	24.78	10.0	885	1225	1440	360	250
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ β -pic	White do	20.75	21.19	23.80	24.18	12.8	890	1230	1440	345	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ γ -pic	Brownish white crystalline	20.86	21.19	23.95	24.13	7.5	875	1230	1450	350	260
Cd(P-dtc) ₂ IQ	do	19.76	20.02	22.48	22.79	14.0	880	1225	1445	350	255
Cd(M-dtc) ₂	White amorphous	25.48	25.75	29.08	29.33	7.0	885	1240	1420	355	250
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ β -pic	Brown, crystalline	20.87	21.03	23.52	23.95	8.7	890	1250	1430	345	260
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ γ -pic	do	20.72	21.03	23.65	23.95	8.9	890	1260	1425	350	260
Cd(M-dtc) ₂ -pip	do	21.28	21.55	24.18	24.54	12.5	895	1250	1425	350	255

P-dtc=piperidyl dithiocarbamate, M-dtc=Morpholyl dithiocarbamate, Py=Pyridine, β -pic= β -Picoline, γ -Pic= γ -Picoline, IQ=Isoquinoline, Pip=Piperidine.

low melting points and low conductance values in acetone, ΔM lying in the range of 6.5-14.0 mhos cm^{-2} indicating non-electrolytic nature of these complexes.

Ir spectra of dithiocarbamates have been studied earlier by Nakamoto *et al.*⁶. Some of the absorption bands and the base adducts have been assigned. The appearance of the bands around 890 and $\sim 1260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands can be assigned as thiol (C-S) and thiocarbonyl (C=S) absorption bands respectively. Shifting of these bands to lower frequencies in case of metal chelates indicates the bonding of both the sulphur atoms to the metal ion. In base-adducts these bands are again shifted to higher frequency region due to the interaction of σ -bonding nitrogen ligands. In addition, most of the free nitrogen ligand absorption bands are modified in the complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. Furthermore, the conclusive evidence of bonding is proved by the occurrence⁸ of $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-S)$ around 350 cm^{-1} and $\sim 250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively in the far ir spectra of the complexes.

Bis(piperidyl or morpholyl dithiocarbamate) Cd(II) complexes are presumably penta-coordinated polymers as inferred from their analysis, high melting point and sparing solubility in common organic solvents. When these metal chelates are refluxed with heterocyclic nitrogen donors for about 2 hrs probably these polymers break up giving rise to pent-coordinated mono-adducts. Hence, the complexes reported in the present investigation are presumably penta-coordinated like the base adducts of β -diketonates^{7,8}, γ -substituted β -diketonates⁹⁻¹⁰ and γ -substituted β -keto arylamide¹¹. However, X-ray crystallography study will reveal the exact stereochemistry of these complexes.

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Spectrophotometric, Potentiometric and Visual Determination of Nitrate with Iron(II)

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NITRATE is directly determined with iron(II) in 9-12 M phosphoric acid by spectrophotometric (in presence of thiocyanate), potentiometric and visual methods using azure A, azure C, methylene blue, methylene green, thionine, cacotheline and ferrion as indicators. The method is extended for the determination of nitrate in fertiliser samples which offers a simple and convenient method over the earlier methods. Potassium which is an important constituent of the fertilisers is also determined by precipitating it quantitatively with nitric acid.

Various methods available for the determination of nitrate need complicated apparatus, are time consuming and approximate. Moreover, different reagents do not react with nitrate in a simple stoichiometric way and give rise to the formation

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of different nitrogen oxides. The widely used Kjeldahl method involves mercury as the catalyst which is hazardous. The iodometric method¹ which is based on the reduction of hydroiodic acid and often referred to in the older literature is not specially to be recommended because even traces of oxygen interfere markedly. Several workers^{2,3} treated nitrate with excess iron(II) and titrating the acid produced with alkali. Knecht and Hibbert⁴ determined nitrate by treating with iron as in Pelouze's methods⁵ and back titrating the iron(III) produced with titanous(III) chloride. Szebelledy^{6,7} has determined nitrate in sulphuric acid medium with ferric nitrosyl complex as indicator.

In the present method, nitrate form of the sample is titrated with iron(II) in 9-12 M phosphoric acid medium by potentiometric method and visual method using azure A, azure C, methylene blue, methylene green, thionine, cacotheline and ferroin as indicators. Nitrate is also determined spectrophotometrically with iron(II) using thiocyanate as the complexing agent. The method is extended to the determination of nitrate in fertilisers and indirectly to the potassium determination.

Materials and Method :

Apparatus : Shimadzu—Double Beam Spectrophotometer (U. V. 140.02). The potentiometric assembly used consists of an Osaw-Crompton potentiometer graduated in millivolts, a galvanometer (both manufactured by Oriental Science Apparatus Workshop, Ambala, India) a saturated calomel reference electrode, a bright platinum rod (0.2 mm diameter) as an indicator electrode and a porous plate salt bridge filled with a saturated solution of KCl. The titration mixture is stirred by means of magnetic stirrer.

Reagents : 0.05 N solutions of potassium nitrate and ferrous ammonium sulphate (in 1M H₂SO₄) are prepared from G. R. samples and standardised conventionally. 1% solution of potassium thiocyanate is prepared. 0.1% solutions of azure A, azure C, thionine, methylene blue, methylene green, ferroin and 0.2% solution of cacotheline are prepared. Ortho-phosphoric acid of pro-analytical grade (E. Merck-India) is used. All other reagents used are of AnalaR grade.

Experimental

The samples containing nitrate or the nitrate fertilisers are taken as such and dissolved in water. Precipitate, if any, is filtered and clear solution is treated as the nitrate sample solution for titration. The samples containing potassium viz., KCl, mureite of potash, potassium fertilisers etc, are dissolved in water, evaporated to dryness and treated with concentrated nitric acid and evaporated again. Now this potassium in nitrate form is used as the titrant.

Spectrophotometric determination : In a series of 25 ml standard flasks, required volume of phosphoric acid to give 10M concentration, known volume of 0.005N nitrate solution or test sample,

1 ml of 0.05N iron(II) solution are added successively and shaken well. Now 1 ml of 1% potassium thiocyanate is added and after 5 mins the absorbance is measured in a 1.00 cm cell at 485 nm. The concentration of the unknown sample is determined from the standard curve.

Titrimetric determination : In the titration vessel required volume of phosphoric acid is taken to give an overall concentration of 11M. Carbon dioxide is passed through for 5 mins. A known volume of iron(II) solution is added followed by 0.2 ml of indicator (0.5 ml for cacotheline) and titrated with the nitrate solution to a sharp colour change of the indicator. 2 ml of 0.384 × 10⁻⁴M solution of Mn(II) is added to catalyse the reaction between iron(II) and nitrate. The passage of carbon dioxide is continued throughout the titration. Alternatively the indicator is excluded and titrated potentiometrically to a sharp break in the potential using the platinum electrode as the indicator electrode and calomel as the reference electrode.

Typical results are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

TABLE 1—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NITRATE WITH IRON(II) IN 11M PHOSPHORIC ACID IN PRESENCE OF THIOCYANATE

Sample	Amount taken (in mgs)	Amount found* (in mgs)	Error %
KNO ₃	26.75	26.78	0.074
NH ₄ NO ₃	19.65	19.63	0.102
Ca. Amm. Nitrate	7.90	7.92	0.253
KCl	10.35	10.84	0.096
K ₂ SO ₄	15.00	14.98	0.193
Mureite of potash	17.00	16.98	0.117
NPK Fertiliser	9.57	9.58	0.104

TABLE 2—POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NITRATE WITH IRON(II) IN 11M PHOSPHORIC ACID MEDIUM

Sample	Potential break for 0.04 ml in mV	Amount taken (in mgs)	Amount found* (in mgs)	Error %
KNO ₃	105	77.50	77.45	0.065
NH ₄ NO ₃	99	36.94	36.28	0.165
Ca. Amm. Nitrate	95	14.50	14.92	0.280
KCl	88	45.75	45.88	0.284
K ₂ SO ₄	84	34.95	34.11	0.408
Mureite of potash	72	55.50	55.25	0.450
NPK Fertiliser	110	27.75	27.67	0.288

TABLE 3—VISUAL DETERMINATION OF NITRATE WITH IRON(II) IN 10M PHOSPHORIC ACID MEDIUM (Cacotheline as indicator)

Sample	Amount taken (in mgs)	Amount found* (in mgs)	Error %
KNO ₃	14.00	14.10	0.71
NH ₄ NO ₃	55.60	55.65	0.271
Ca. Amm. Nitrate	45.75	45.86	0.24
KCl	67.75	67.96	0.31
K ₂ SO ₄	34.46	34.30	0.46
Mureite of potash	36.34	36.30	0.11
NPK Fertiliser	21.00	21.15	0.71

*Average of three readings.

Results and Discussion

The addition of nitrate to iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium will oxidise iron(II) to iron(III). The quantitative nature of the reaction between nitrate and iron(II) was studied by Krishnamurty⁸ *et al.* The iron(III) produced is in proportion with the nitrate reduced. Basing on this, the iron(III)-thiocyanate complex is developed and the colour of the complex, which is in proportion with the nitrate concentration is measured spectrophotometrically.

In potentiometric and visual methods the passage of carbon dioxide is carried throughout the titration to avoid the aerial oxidation of iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium.

As the titration medium 9-12.5M phosphoric acid is suggested with an optimum concentration of 11 M. Below the concentration of 9 M the colour change of the indicator is sluggish and low values are obtained.

In the particular sample of NPK fertiliser taken there is the presence of only ammonium ion but no other metal ions or nitrate are present to estimable limits. The simplest and most widely used method for the elimination of the effect of ammonium ions is ignition (350°-450°), which causes ammonium salts to sublime or decompose. At these temperatures potassium salts are practically non-volatile⁹. Ammonium nitrate is the most readily decomposed of all the ammonium salts and therefore it is eliminated automatically during the treatment of ignition with nitric acid.

In the case of mureite of potash (fertiliser) sample neither the ammonium nor calcium nor nitrate ions are present in the sample taken. However, there is a possibility of having calcium ions in certain cases which can be eliminated by adding oxalic acid.

If the sample of fertiliser contains nitrate also, it can be estimated directly with the same method without converting the sample to nitrate form and then accounting for the estimation of potassium.

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Oscillating Iodine Clock Reaction in Presence of Chloride Ions

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BRIGGS-RAUSCHER Iodine Clock oscillating reaction has been previously studied in aqueous perchloric¹, sulphuric¹, nitric² and phosphoric acid³ media. It has also been reported earlier that the reaction does not take place in hydrochloric acid² medium as the chloride ions act as inhibitors⁴. In the present investigation it has been shown that the reaction is possible in hydrochloric acid medium and in presence of added chloride ions in phosphoric acid medium, provided the chloride ion concentration is not high. A mechanism of chloride inhibition has also been proposed.

Experimental

Three stock solutions were prepared separately and then mixed in equal volumes at room temperature. One was of hydrogen peroxide, another of iodate and phosphoric acid and the third of acetoacetic ester, starch and manganese. Cycling was initiated by adding the solution containing iodate. In order to study the effect of chloride ions, an aqueous sodium chloride solution was prepared and the concentration of chloride ions in the mixture was varied suitably in a systematic manner before initiating the reaction. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred at a more or less fixed slow rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The time period of oscillation was recorded visually from the beautiful appearance or disappearance of blue color.

For studying the reaction in HCl medium, a solution of iodate in hydrochloric acid (in place of phosphoric acid) was prepared and cycling was initiated by adding this solution.

All solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations in the Tables 1 and 2 refer to

TABLE 1—IODINE CLOCK REACTION IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE IONS

[Cl ⁻]	Induction period in secs	Color change noted for recording time period	Total time of oscillation	Total No. of oscillations
(I) nil	16	Appearance of blue color	14'8"	52
(II) 0.01(M)	21	—do—	10'2"	25
(III) 0.02(M)	27	—do—	9'1"	24
(IV) 0.03(M)	41	—do—	9'35"	21
(V) 0.04(M)	68	—do—	8'55"	21
(VI) 0.0425(M)	—	No visible Oscillation	—	—

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